

**A STUDY ON THE OCCUPATIONAL ADJUSTMENT OF MALE AND FEMALE
PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS**

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Abstract: - The review was attempted to concentrate on the change of male and female physical education teachers in Jammu and Kashmir UT. The examiner took hundred (100) teachers (50 male and 50 female as samples. The information was gathered with the assistance of Bell's adjustment inventory (adult form). The inventory has five regions, viz, home, wellbeing, social, profound and occupational. The analysis of the data revealed that In conclusion, it was found that the male grade teachers have more occupational problems when contrasted with female elementary teachers. The study further revealed that both the groups do not differ on health and social adjustment dimension of Bell's adjustment inventory

Keyword: Adjustment, male, female, physical education.

Introduction:-

The word reference significance of the word 'change' is to fit, make reasonable, adjust, organize, alter, blend or make reporter. Hence, when we make a change between two things, we adjust or alter either of them to relate to one another. As per Darwin's (1859) hypothesis of development, those species which adjusted effectively to the requests of living, made due and increased while other people who didn't, vanished. Subsequently, the adaptation or changing of oneself or one's environmental elements as per the requests of the outer climate turned into the essential requirement for our endurance. Today is as evident with us all as it was with the Darwin's crude species. As indicated by James Drever (1952) said "change implies the alteration to make up for or meet extraordinary circumstances". He takes acclimation to be the available resources to assist the person with fulfilling the needs of changed conditions by adjusting or altering his past approaches to doing or confronting things. C.V. Great (1959) characterized change as " it is the most common way of finding and embracing methods of conduct reasonable to the climate or the progressions in the climate" Change includes the satisfaction of an individual's necessities as represented by the requests of different ecological circumstances. This isn't, notwithstanding, a one way process: an individual keeps up with the harmony among himself and his environmental factors either by changing his own way of behaving or by changing the climate. In the specific circumstance, as Arkoff (1968) states "change is the collaboration between an individual and his current circumstance. How one change in a specific circumstance relies on one's very own qualities as likewise the conditions of the circumstance? All in all, both individual and natural elements work one next to the other in change. An individual is changed assuming he is acclimated to himself and to his current circumstance. One of the significant inquiries relating to change of in-administration essential educators is with regards to how the different showing abilities contribute towards making their instructing powerful. The truth of the matter is in the absence of openness to these showing abilities, an educator might find it challenging to boil down to the degrees of grade younger students and neglect to picture his/her part in managing various issues at this level and thus the issue emerges of his/her self-acclimation to the circumstance he/she is relegated to work in. Fundamentally it is brought up in many explores that simple ownership of a certificate or degree in educating doesn't guarantee dominance. Other than techniques must be helped and polished comparable to topic e.g; if there should be an occurrence of rudimentary instructor schooling prepared educator and an optional prepared instructor are relegated to educate at an essential level, their strategies for instructing would contrast. This being thus, a rudimentary educator schooling prepared educator gets restrictive preparation in educating at essential level while an optional prepared educator does at an auxiliary level. Different variables i.e, ability lacks ought to be recognized so educators could be better taught in eliminating their expertise

abandons. It might anticipate the improvement in their schooling a subsequently in their scholastic exhibition. Nonetheless, it is essential to distinguish the expertise lacks and factors adding to mental part of educator's character. Albeit many explores have been finished in the field of educator schooling however exceptionally restricted examinations seem to have been completed with respect to in-support instructors. Analysts should accordingly coordinate towards testing such center showing abilities as changes of instructors educating at essential level

1. Objectives:-

- To assess the social adjustment of male and female physical education teachers.
- To assess the emotional adjustment of male and female physical education teachers.
- To compare the occupational adjustment of male and female physical education teachers.

2. Hypothesis:-

- Male and female physical education teachers differsignificantly on Social adjustment.
- Male and female physical education teachers differsignificantly on Emotional adjustment.
- Male and female physical education teachers differ significantly on occupational adjustment.

Review of Literature

Chennoufi et al. (2012), The aim of this study was to evaluate burnout among a population of Tunisian teachers and to examine the professional stressors associated with teachers' burnout. This Study was a transversal study conducted over five months (from October 2009 to February 2010) and it concerned teachers working in the public high schools of Manouba (Tunisia). The participants completed a self-questionnaire dealing with professional stressors. Five types of professional stressors were identified in the literature: bad working conditions, work overload, administrative difficulties, organizational factors and difficulties with pupils and their relatives. They were also explored by the scale of the burnout: the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI), the best-studied measurement of burnout in the literature. We used the French version of the MBI adapted to educational settings. It is a scale composed of 22 items and three dimensions: emotional exhaustion (nine items), dehumanization (five items) and reduced personal accomplishment (eight items). In our study, we considered that a teacher was suffering from burnout when at least two among the three dimensions of this scale were pathological. From the total number of teachers working in public high schools of Manouba (n=876), only 398 teachers filled in our questionnaires. Hence the rate of participation was 45.4%. The mean age of those participants was 40.04 years. 52.3% of them were women (sex ratio=0.91) and the great majority was married (81.8%). The burnout syndrome was found in 21% of those teachers: Moderate professional exhaustion was found in 16.4% of cases and severe professional exhaustion was found in 4.6%. A high emotional exhaustion was found in 27.4% of cases. A percentage of 16.1 of participants had a high dehumanization and 45.5% of them were susceptible to reduced personal accomplishment. The majority of teachers (66.4%) declared being stressed at work. The professional stressors reported by the teachers were in decreasing order of rate: bad working conditions (80.3%), overload work (75.2%), administrative difficulties (70.4%), difficulties with pupils and their relatives (64.4%) and finally organizational factors (57.1%). In our study, we found a strong association between burnout syndrome among teachers and three types of professional stressors which were: bad working conditions (p=0.0017), administrative difficulties (p=0.005) and difficulties with pupils and their relatives (p=0.005). The organizational factors and the work overload were not associated with the burnout syndrome. The job of teaching accumulates many difficulties. Some Tunisian teachers couldnot tolerate this professional stress and develop a burnout. This syndrome leads to a teachers' psychological distress with the risk of an increase in absenteeism at work. So, we hope that this study will give rise to future research on stress, coping and burnout among Tunisian teachers, with theoretical aims as well as practical applications to prevent and reduce the risk of this problem.

Kaveh et al. (2014), the effect of teachers stress on teaching and learning processes, the researchers decided to provide a stress management program based on Transactional Model to solve this problem. To investigate the effect of Transactional Model- based Teaching and the Ordinary Education Curriculum- based Teaching programs on Yazd teachers. The study was a semi- experimental one. The sample population (200 people) was selected using categorized method. The data were collected via PSS Questionnaire and a questionnaire which its validity and reliability had been proved. Eight teaching sessions were held for 60-90 min. Evaluation was performed in three steps. The data was described and analyzed using SPSS software version 15. Value of $P < 0.05$ was considered as significant. The participants were 200 people of Yazd teachers of primary schools. Mean age of group 1 and 2 was 42.05 ± 5.69 and 41.25 ± 5.89 respectively. Independent T- Test indicated a significant mean score ($p = 0.000$) due to perceived stress of interference groups in post interference step and follow-up one respectively. Results showed a decreasing effect of both programs, but the Transactional Model- based interference indicated to decrease stress more than the other.

Serrano et al.(2014), To analyse the Endocrine and Mood Responses to two Working Days in Female Teachers, studied on a considerable amount of work stress is present in school teachers, one of the occupational groups with the highest levels of job strain and burnout. As chronic stress produces significant modifications in emotional adjustment and neuro - endocrine functioning, we aimed to investigate the role of these work stress constructs in the endocrine and mood responses of a group of female teachers during two working days (WD) at different moments in the academic year. We studied mood as well as levels of cortisol and testosterone, representative of a predominant catabolic or anabolic balance. Our results showed that higher "control" was associated with higher positive mood ($p = .028$ on WD1 and $p = .057$ on WD2) and salivary testosterone (Tsal) ($p = .022$ on WD1), whereas "demands" and "total job strain" were related to negative mood ($p = .011$ and $p = .015$, respectively). Participants with higher scores on "total burnout" and "emotional exhaustion" also had higher negative mood ($p < .05$ in all cases). Depersonalization correlated positively with negative mood ($p = .019$ and $p = .006$ on WD1 and WD2, respectively). Finally, personal accomplishment showed an inverse relationship with negative mood ($p = .038$ on WD2). These results are useful for job risk prevention and interventions that should focus on the control dimension of the job strain questionnaire and on personal accomplishment from the burnout scale.

3. Materials and methods

Sample

For this study, a sample of 50 male and 50 female physical education instructors was chosen. The sample was drawn from Jammu and Kashmir UT using random sampling procedures.

Tool used

The data was collected with the help of Bell Adjustment Inventory (adult form). The inventory has five areas, viz home, health, social, emotional and occupational.

Statistical treatment:-

The data has been analysed by applying t- test in order to find the significant differences between the means of male and female physical education teachers on various areas of adjustment.

4. Analysis and interpretation:-

Table 1. Mean comparison of male and female physical physical education on Social adjustment:

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Remarks
Male physical physical education	50	9.38	2.10	0.26	Insignificant
Male physical physical education	50	9.28	1.98		

The table 1 shows the mean comparison of male and female physical physical education on social

adjustment. The table reveals that the male and female school teachers do not differ significantly on social adjustment. It indicates that both the groups have similar adjustment

Table 2. Mean comparison of male and female physical physical education on Emotional adjustment:

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Remarks
Male physical physical education	50	11.40	2.33	6.74	Significant at 0.01 level
Male physical physical education	50	15.04	3.21		

The table 4 shows the mean comparison of male and female physical physical education on emotional adjustment. The table reveals that the male and female school teachers differ significantly on emotional adjustment. It indicates that female physical physical education have more emotional adjustment than male physical physical education.

Table 3. Mean comparison of male and female physical education teachers on occupational adjustment:

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-value	Remarks
Male physical physical education	50	9.18	1.97	3.18	Significant at 0.01 level
Male physical education teachers	50	8.00	1.96		

The table 3 shows the mean comparison of male and female physical education teachers on occupational adjustment. The table reveals that the male and female school teachers differ significantly on occupational adjustment. It indicates that male physical education teachers have more problems with regard to their occupational adjustment than female physical education teachers.

Conclusion:-

In conclusion, it was found that the female physical education teachers have more problems on home adjustment, emotional adjustment and on total score of adjustment than male physical education teachers of Jammu and kashmir UT. It was further found that the male physical education teachers have more occupational problems as compared to female physical education teachers. The study further revealed that both the groups do not differ on health and social adjustment dimension of Bell's adjustment inventory.

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